
The Basis of Studying the Scientific Interpretation of the Problem of Jealous

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Annotation. *The article spoke about the observation of two conditions in the phenomenon (in a unique aspect) of feelings of jealousy, positive and negative emotions manifested in human relationships, the connection of a person with living conditions, mental states, the perception of the human psyche, life, his attitude to it, the complex of subjective experiences associated with their spiritual acceptance.*

Keywords: *jealousy, family, personality, human psyche, happy life, verbal creativity, decency, positive and negative emotions dignity, attention, upbringing, family, marriage and love.*

INTRODUCTION

The human society came into being, and the positive and negative emotions manifested in human relations became one of the important issues in the center of attention of all people. Therefore, since ancient times, the phenomenon of jealousy has occupied a special place among emotional relations in examples of folklore, epics, songs and fairy tales, in the thoughts and views of sages.

It can be observed that in almost the same period, in different places, in the teachings of Buddha in India and Confucius in China, an idea and a view was formed: "Do not attribute to others what you do not attribute to yourself." In Confucius's legacy, relations between people, loving people, and not being jealous of their honor are given a lot of space. It is interpreted that "to love people and have a warm relationship is not to deny oneself, but to see other people and oneself equally."

In the works of the oriental scientist Abu Ali Ibn Sina, "Risalai ishq" and "Donishmandnama", every person expresses his feelings in his manners, behavior and attitude to others in order to be happy.

In our opinion, this opinion of the scholar shows the cognitive, conative and affective side of behavior in psychology and indicates the need for scientific research of this feeling.

According to Yusuf Khos Hajib and Abu Nasr Farabi, one of the Shark thinkers, the basic key to being close friends with people is "language, because of language, a person polishes his knowledge and intellect." We understand that it is necessary to pay attention to human relations through thoughts such as

"speaking a word deliberately makes it great, or if it is not spoken deliberately, it lowers its value". But in these views, only values such as love, friendship, and doing good are paid attention to as a manifestation of human relations. Although jealousy, envy, lack of respect for others, possessiveness in human relationships have been observed in life since ancient times, attention is paid to the need to do good from the point of view of not spreading these vices.

For a long time, the phenomenon of jealousy from emotional relationships and its manifestation in a person was considered not a subject of scientific research, but a subject of literature, art and other fields. In psychology, emotional-emotional relations, feelings of jealousy in interpersonal relations and its classification, forms, and mechanisms are important and affect human life.

From the review of the studied literature, it became clear that the direct study of the feeling of jealousy and the creation of the first works on this topic correspond to the second half of the 19th century. A. Adler, Z. Freud, E. Fromm, K. Horney, K. Jung and others from foreign psychologists have shed some light on the feeling of jealousy belonging to emotional relationships. These scientists teach the person experiencing jealousy to hide it not only from others, but also from themselves.

Sigmund Freud, the scientist who created the first concept of the problem of jealousy, wrote in his work "On Jealousy, Paranoia and Some Neurotic Mechanisms": "...where there is jealousy and envy in a person's behavior, he is subject to strong repression. ..." he shouts.

According to Melanie Klein, a supporter of Z. Freud's ideas, a person's feeling of jealousy is based on harm and comes from the fear of losing a loved one.

According to Karen Horney, "neurotic jealousy, unlike the jealousy of a healthy person, may be an adequate response to the risk of losing someone's love, which is proportionate to the risk. It is characterized by constant fear of losing someone's property or love.

American A. Maslow explains that human needs are related to emotional issues. Among human needs, the need to strive for good relationships - to be loved, to be needed, to belong to some kind of community, etc., shows that confidence and interest in a person, activity and life will be effective, and in this regard, needs will be fulfilled.

It is known that jealousy does not arise by itself. E. Hatfield and G. Walster, one of Farb's psychologists, explain the causes and motives of jealousy in the first place based on the psychological effect of treating another person as one's own property. In our view, it would be appropriate to conduct in-depth research in order to present such a conclusion.

In understanding the specific aspects of jealousy, it is appropriate to quote the opinions of foreign psychologists V. Frankl and R. May. Although the above-mentioned Z. Freud describes jealousy as an affective state, W. Frankl, a representative of existential psychology, substantiates the idea of how harmful the phenomenon of jealousy can be for a person: "...jealousy is stupidity in any case, because it appear too early or too late. ... A jealous person doubts his partner, does not understand that he can really lose him. Therefore, according to W. Frankl, it is not right for a person who loves his partner to constantly make demands on his partner, strict demands will inevitably cause dissatisfaction."

R. May, a representative of humanistic psychology, focuses on the fact that jealousy shows a person's weakness and the owner of jealousy has a sense of ownership. According to him, through jealousy, a person does not feel that he is a threat to another person, and the feeling of jealousy is manifested when a person seeks strength from love, when he does not value himself enough, when he considers himself in a helpless position.

R. May proves that jealousy originates from the inherent ambivalence in relationships. According to him, a person loves, but at the same time hates. It should be noted that this scientist determined that the feeling of jealousy is closely related to personal qualities such as self-worth, a sense of security, and emotional stability. In the research part of our dissertation work, we determine as a research task to give importance to aspects of the relationship of the feeling of jealousy with personal qualities identified by R. May.

D. Y. Raygorodsky considers the origin of jealousy to be related to the man's dominant position in the family and the woman's financial or other dependence on her husband. In society, the moral standards of men and women were significantly different. Men were allowed to indulge in frivolous activities and hobbies, but women's behavior was judged much more harshly.

V. T. Lisovsky emphasizes that there is nothing more aggressive than unreasonable jealousy in love, and he emphasizes that jealousy is related to contradictions in love, family and marriage. In addition, it explains that negligence or betrayal of one of the spouses, depriving one of the children of the family of affection are the reasons.

According to V.T. Lisovsky, jealousy has the following causes:

1. Indifference in the attitude of one of the lovers;
2. Previous relationships of one of the couples;
3. Gossip and slander of jealous people.

From the analysis of scientific works on jealousy and its psychology by foreign scientists, it can be seen that in the content and causes of jealousy, the psyche manifests itself unconsciously and is explained by

such results as the presence of neurotic needs for the feeling of a person, strong personality traits or natural evolutionary mechanisms.

K.Izard, E.Erikson, I.S.Kon and others, among the famous psychologists of the world, paid attention to the issues of explaining the impact of emotional relationships on personality development, the negative consequences of jealousy.

Research on Jealousy Problems (Author's Analysis)

Foreign scientists who studied the problem of jealousy		
Psychoanalysis	Z. Freyd, M.Klyayn, K.Xorni, A.Adler, P.Kutter	The essence of jealousy, classification of types of jealousy, observed jealousy between parents and children, jealousy in childhood, types of jealousy between couples (spouses) have been determined.
Humanistic direction	R.Mey, V.Frankl, E.Fromm, A.Maslou	The causes of jealousy, a sense of ownership, self-esteem, jealousy in the field of interpersonal relations, negative complications of jealousy have been identified.
An evolutionary approach	D.Bass, D.Barrels, A.Elelayti, R.Deystra	The content of romantic jealousy, various manifestations of jealousy have been empirically studied. Jealousy and violence, jealousy and masculinity, jealousy and femininity are identified.
Scientists from the CIS countries studied the problem of jealousy		
Psychology of the Orthodox religion	T.A.Florenskaya, D.A.Avdeyev	The content and essence of the types of spiritual, emotional, evil jealousy are explained.
Patho-psychology of personality	Ye.N. Terentyev, N. V. Dmitriyeva, S. P. Korolenko, A. N.Volkova	The role of jealousy in interpersonal relationships in the family, the factors of pathological jealousy, and the symptoms of jealousy are revealed.
Personality psychology	Y. Spiridonov, Ye. P.Ilin, N. V.Dmitriyeva A.V.Sergeyeva	Classifications of jealousy, the main types are described. Empirical studies have been conducted on the relationship between personality traits and jealousy indicators.

Alfred Adler interprets jealousy as a complex relationship in explanation. And this is considered a characteristic of character, that is, a personality trait that comes from pretending to be helpless and, as a result, a superiority complex.

P. Kutter interprets jealousy as the effect of a person's childhood experiences. According to him, parents cannot take care of their children all the time in the upbringing of the family, the hatred and revenge that arise during jealousy are mainly self-protective and are aimed at restoring the narcissistic balance.

Thus, the phenomenon of jealousy refers to the behavior that is manifested in the form of internal and emotional reactions of a person who is involved in emotional relationships with a loved one, partner, friend, colleague in his activities (communication, relationship).

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